

Strategic review and feasibility study of Open Access models

Prepared on behalf of NHS Wales e-Library and WHELF

April 2026

Strategic review and feasibility study of Open Access models

Report commissioned by:

NHS Wales e-Library and WHELP

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Contact:

NHS Wales e-Library (DHCW): Rachel Sully, Head of Research and Innovation (Interim),
Rachel.Sully@wales.nhs.uk

WHELP: Alison Harding, Executive Head of Library and Learning Resources, University of Wales Trinity Saint David:
a.harding@uwtsd.ac.uk

Report authors:

Rob Johnson, Angharad Roberts, Frances Palmer

www.research-consulting.com

Robert Francis, Carreg Las Limited

Contact:

angharad.roberts@research-consulting.com

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Executive Summary

Project background NHS Wales e-Library and its Service Board (managed by Digital Health and Care Wales (DHCW)) / Wales Higher Education Libraries Forum (WHELF) commissioned Research Consulting to conduct a strategic review of Open Access publishing models for health and care research in Wales.

Describing the landscape of OA in higher education and the NHS

Strong OA publishing within WHELF... This report summarises the current context for OA publishing in WHELF organisations, including the pressure on finance in Higher Education, and the scale of WHELF publishing activity over the last ten years.

The report also describes OA awareness, infrastructure and implementation within WHELF organisations, WHELF engagement with NHS Wales and existing University Presses in Wales.

...but gaps and challenges for NHS Wales, especially without academic co-authors NHS Wales benefits from OA publication routes available to co-authors in academic institutions. Where these are not present, levels of OA are noticeably lower – less than half of such outputs from the last ten years are available through OA.

The report also considers the benefits of OA publishing to NHS Wales, types of content which would be suitable for wider sharing, current approaches to recording published outputs from NHS Wales organisations and case studies from other health systems.

Appetite and options for growing OA publishing in Wales

Drivers for developing OA in Wales for WHELF and NHS Wales Financial pressures facing higher education in Wales mean that there is interest in developing other routes to OA publication, including Green and Diamond options. NHS Wales faces particular challenges in low levels of awareness of OA publication options, and easy, straightforward routes to OA publication for staff without academic co-authors.

There is significant appetite for increasing OA publishing in Wales There is significant appetite for increasing OA publishing in NHS Wales, supported by the perception that there is scope for increased volume of quality outputs, opportunities to build on previous initiatives and existing trust between WHELF members and the NHS, and value in implementing new systems and approaches at an appropriate level.

There is appetite for potential Diamond OA publishing by NHS Wales, although there is also an acknowledgment of the challenges and limitations of this model in the context of current resource constraints in the NHS and Higher Education.

The report presents four options for consideration The report presents four options for consideration:

- Option 1: do nothing
- Option 2: implement an NHS Wales repository

- Option 3: pilot a Diamond OA Journal
- Option 4: establish a Diamond OA Press

Options 2-4 are summarised in Figure 1 – a fuller version of this is shown in Figure 8 in section 5.

The most immediate benefit of these approaches would be for NHS Wales, but may offer advantages to WHELF in the longer term

Although the most immediate benefit in developing OA routes for NHS Wales staff would be to the NHS, there would be scope over time to combine or integrate NHS Wales OA approaches with those in WHELF institutions. Similarly, new OA publications aimed primarily at NHS staff could also publish work by academics and students at WHELF institutions.

Option 2, implementation of an NHS Wales repository, would benefit from potential informal support from WHELF institutions such as advice or expertise in repository management. Options 3 and 4 would benefit from academic and institutional support such as reviewing or editorial engagement, or arrangements for potential hosting or technical support.

Figure 1. Summary of options 2-4.

	NHS Wales repository	Diamond OA Journal	Diamond OA Press
Amount of OA facilitated	Stronger	Moderate	Moderate
Potential for integration	Stronger	Moderate	Moderate
Scalable	Stronger	Moderate	Moderate
Sustainable	Stronger	Moderate	Weaker
Feasibility	Stronger	Moderate	Weaker
Technical feasibility	Stronger	Stronger	Moderate
Risks	Stronger	Moderate	Weaker
Admin burden	Moderate	Moderate	Weaker
Complexity of governance	Stronger	Moderate	Weaker
Quality oversight	Moderate	Stronger	Stronger
Finance	Stronger	Moderate	Weaker
Cost vs value	Stronger	Moderate	Moderate
Staff time	Moderate	Moderate	Weaker

Key – colour coding indicates that for each of the criteria, each option is relatively:

Stronger	Moderate	Weaker
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Recommendations

We make eight recommendations for taking this work forward

We recommend the following steps as **enabling work**, which would primarily be undertaken by NHS Wales:

1. Continue with ongoing work to make affiliation and identity citing more consistent;

2. Develop and implement NHS Wales OA policy (based on DHCW policy, Public Health Wales (PHW) publishing guidance);
3. Engage with Cardiff University Press and University of Wales Press to explore specific opportunities for potential collaboration or partnership; and
4. Make connections with Open Health Research Ireland Network (OHRIN) regarding their work to develop a Diamond OA journal for health and social care practitioners, hosted at Trinity College Dublin.

There is further work to do to **understand the potential audiences** for a potential Diamond OA journal:

5. Map NHS Wales communities and potential scope of pilot Diamond OA Journal; and
6. Engage with professional associations and / or professional qualification course providers to explore potential scope for an NHS Wales journal.

Based on the findings of this project, we recommend **implementing the following options**:

7. Option 2: Build and manage an NHS Wales repository. This could inform the repository system procurement process to be undertaken by DHCW in autumn 2026:
 - a. Prioritise to maximise potential of Green OA for NHS Wales only;
 - b. Consider how this might support future discussions regarding a cross-Wales (HE and NHS) research repository.
8. Option 3: Pilot Diamond OA journal:
 - a. Trial in one specific area

Implementing these two options would require additional funding and a business case should be submitted to the Welsh Government.

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1. Introduction

1.1 Background

Context

NHS Wales e-Library and its Service Board (managed by Digital Health and Care Wales (DHCW)) / Wales Higher Education Libraries Forum (WHELF) commissioned Research Consulting to conduct a strategic review of Open Access publishing models for health and care research in Wales.

The study has been undertaken against the background of the UK higher education and research sector negotiations, in collaboration with Jisc, to develop **next generation Open Access** agreements with the publishers Elsevier, Springer Nature, Taylor & Francis, Wiley and Sage. In December 2025, all five of these publishers met the sector-agreed thresholds for acceptance. These negotiations follow on from Jisc's **Review of transitional agreements in the UK** (Jisc, 2024) and **SCONUL's response** (SCONUL, 2024).

This work has also been undertaken in the context of recent examples of initiatives to support Open Access in NHS Wales, including the creation of the **Digital Health and Care Wales Research and Knowledge Repository** and the **DHCW Open Access Policy**.

Definitions of key terms are included in the glossary in Appendix A.

Project team

This project was managed by Angharad Roberts (Senior Analyst) in conjunction with Robert Francis (Carreg Las). Quality assurance was provided by Rob Johnson (Managing Director). Translation support was provided by Nerys Hurford, (Nerys Hurford Cyf./Ltd).

1.2 Methodology

Project aims

This study had two aims:

- Identify whether a **Diamond Open Press** for the publication of medical, health and social care works would **accelerate the shift towards Open Access for NHS and Higher Education institutions in Wales**. Diamond open access publishing makes research freely available to all readers with no costs to authors or their institutions.
- Take a deep dive into current publishing practices across NHS Wales's Health Boards, Trusts and Special Health Authorities and consider whether a **local or national Open Access Policy, Institutional Repository and/or Open Press** would enhance the research profile of NHS Wales.

Methods used

The project approach was designed using the Double Diamond framework developed by the **Design Council** (see **Figure 2**). This delivery framework is an ideal approach to projects that feature a significant amount of co-creation and where later phases are dependent on outcomes from earlier phases of work. The specific methods used included:

- desk research and data analysis using the online bibliographic database and research intelligence tool **Dimensions**;

- stakeholder engagement with interviewees in NHS Wales (16), people within Welsh universities (15) and experts with experience of Open Access and / or the health and care information and publishing landscape beyond Wales (8 people); and
- an interim workshop in December 2025 (13 participants), including interactive discussion and participation facilitated using **Mentimeter**.

Stakeholder engagement took place between November 2025 and January 2026 and a list of participants is included in Appendix B. Interviews were offered in Welsh and English and briefing notes for the stakeholder engagement were prepared bilingually.

Figure 2. Double-diamond approach and high-level overview of the project work packages

Structure of this report

This project has been commissioned and managed jointly by Digital Health and Care Wales (DHCW) and the Wales Higher Education Libraries Forum (WHELP) and this report presents findings from the perspectives of both Higher Education and NHS Wales stakeholders, describing:

- section 2: the current landscape of OA publishing within WHELP, which establishes the overall scale of academic publishing in the country and in health and care subjects specifically;
- section 3: the current landscape of OA publishing within NHS Wales, including patterns of collaboration with academic institutions in and beyond Wales;
- section 4: stakeholder appetites for increasing OA publishing in this field;
- section 5: options analysis; and
- section 6: conclusions and recommendations.

Use of artificial intelligence (AI) The transcription and analysis of the qualitative data used to prepare this report was assisted by **Microsoft Copilot Pro**, an AI-powered tool that helps generate code and text. Copilot Pro was used to provide transcripts and additional summary notes from the interviews and from the workshop, which were recorded in Microsoft Teams.

Acknowledgements This project would not have been possible without the review, input, and critical advice we received from project leads and partners. In particular, we thank:

- The project leads from NHS Wales e-Library and its Service Board (managed by Digital Health and Care Wales) and WHELF: Rachel Sully (Head of Research and Innovation (Interim) and NHS Wales e-Library and Knowledge Service Manager) and Alison Harding (Executive Head of Library and Learning Resources, University of Wales Trinity Saint David).
- Our associate Robert Francis (Director, Carreg Las) for his input into the stakeholder consultation and his critical review of our findings.
- The members of the NHS and higher education communities, publishers and open access experts who generously volunteered their time to participate in this project.

2. The current landscape of OA publishing within WHELF

This section summarises the current publishing landscape within WHELF

This section summarises the current context for OA publishing in WHELF organisations, including the pressure on finances in Welsh Higher Education, and the scale of WHELF publishing activity over the last ten years.

This section also describes OA awareness, infrastructure and implementation within WHELF organisations, WHELF engagement with NHS Wales and perspectives on Diamond OA.

This illustrates the overall scale of academic publishing in Wales and in health and care subjects specifically, setting the scene for describing the landscape of OA publishing in NHS Wales in section 3.

2.1 Overview of WHELF OA publishing trends 2015-24

Across all WHELF publications, OA has grown but is tapering off

Search results from the [Dimensions database](#) show a clear trend of growth in Open Access publications¹ across all disciplinary areas covered by WHELF members (excluding the Open University) over the last ten years.

Numbers of Open Access outputs have nearly doubled between 2015 and 2024 and make up 63% of total WHELF publications over that time. This reflects an overall growth in total publication volume, rather than commensurate reductions in numbers of closed publications.

It is also notable that levels of OA publication have plateaued and then slightly reduced since 2021. OA and closed publication trends for all WHELF publications are shown in solid lines in Figure 3.

WHELF health-related publications follow a similar trajectory

This pattern of substantial growth in OA publication is also apparent in the approximately one third of WHELF publications which relate specifically to fields of research focused on biomedical and clinical sciences and health sciences.

OA publications make up 71% of total WHELF publications in these fields over the last ten years, reflecting generally higher levels of OA in these subject areas.

Again, levels of OA publication have tapered off slightly within these subject areas since 2022. OA and closed publication trends for these WHELF subject areas are shown in the dashed lines in Figure 3.

¹ "Publications" in Dimensions includes journal articles, preprints, books and book chapters, and conference proceedings. It also includes search results from pre-print services, such as MedRxiv. Dimensions categorises these results as Green OA. **481** results from MedRxiv were recorded from WHELF authors during the period 2019-2024; **201** search results for NHS Wales were from MedRxiv. Other pre-print sources are also covered by Dimensions, such as ArXiv and BioRxiv.

Figure 3. WHELF publications 2015-24.

2.2 OA awareness, infrastructure and implementation

Generally, awareness of OA is high in WHELF organisations, driven by Research Excellence Framework and funder requirements

Interviewees from WHELF universities describe generally high levels of awareness of OA requirements, with Research Excellence Framework (REF) requirements driving both institutional development and prioritisation of OA and levels of engagement by individual academics. All universities have OA policies in place.

Individual funder requirements also drive levels of OA publication, with particular reference made to UKRI, NIHR, Wellcome and other charitable funders. Reflecting the diversity of Welsh universities, there are varying levels of funding available from block grants and some use of institutional or departmental funds for OA costs (such as Article Processing Charges).

A link is also made between positive research culture and use of OA routes for publication.

“A positive research culture is one that is committed to open publishing, and it’s committed to sharing your research findings, sharing your methodology, sharing what approach you’ve taken in your work.” – Academic, HE Wales

Jisc-negotiated deals with major publishers are a major feature of Welsh universities approach to OA...

Jisc-negotiated deals, particularly with the “big 5” publishers (Elsevier, Springer Nature, Taylor & Francis, Wiley and Sage) have formed a significant part of WHELF universities’ approach to OA.

These arrangements enable “read and publish” access for institutions to access published content (the “read” element) and to facilitate publishing in relevant titles by the institutions’ academics without requiring the payment of Article Processing Charges (the “publish” element).

This project took place as negotiations facilitated by Jisc were underway to develop **next generation Open Access** agreements - Elsevier, Springer Nature, Taylor & Francis, Wiley and Sage met the sector-agreed thresholds for acceptance in December 2025.

There was a broad consensus among most interviewees within Welsh universities regarding reservations about the sustainability of these big deals (also known as transformative or transitional agreements), and whether they provide value for money in a time of significant financial challenges in Higher Education. Uncertainty about what these deals would be transitioning to, or what "transformation" they will deliver, was also clear.

"The word transition suggests it moves to something else, but we're not really seeing what that something else looks like." – Librarian, HE Wales

"Transformative agreements with the publishers are becoming increasingly problematic, they're very expensive and it doesn't work for the sector" – Librarian, HE Wales

...although in at least one institution there is a significant shift in emphasis to Green OA

In at least one institution, challenges presented by the big deal model have contributed to a shift towards encouraging the use of Green open access. This includes a researcher education programme about Green OA, emphasising the importance of using Rights Retention statements and applying Creative Commons (CC-BY) licences, as well as ensuring they make use of the university's institutional repository.

"This is an interesting time because we are likely to be moving away from gold Open Access publishing towards predominantly Green Open Access" – Librarian, HE Wales

All WHELF universities have institutional repositories in place, of varying levels of maturity and scale

All 8 Welsh universities have some form of institutional repository infrastructure in place, of varying levels of maturity and scale. These range from 500 items in a repository provided in the GuildHE shared service platform to a repository with over 144k outputs (Table 1).

Systems include standalone repositories which sit within Library teams, or Current Research Information Systems (CRIS) with integrated repository functionality. Multiple universities note a shift in responsibility for managing these systems from libraries (which tend to maintain standalone repositories) to Research Services (which tend to have greater responsibility for managing CRIS platforms, supporting the whole research lifecycle).

Table 1. University institutional repositories.

University	URL	Number of items	Platform
Aberystwyth	https://research.aber.ac.uk/	27,000 research outputs	Elsevier Pure
Bangor	https://research.bangor.ac.uk/en/	32,559 research outputs	Elsevier Pure
Cardiff Metropolitan	https://pure.cardiffmet.ac.uk/	8,205 research outputs	Elsevier Pure
Cardiff University	https://orca.cardiff.ac.uk/	144,030 items	EPrints
Swansea University	https://cronfa.swan.ac.uk/	46,854 items	Bespoke Research Information System
University of South Wales	https://pure.southwales.ac.uk/en/	15,257 research outputs	Elsevier Pure
University of Wales Trinity Saint David	https://repository.uwtsd.ac.uk/	1,935 items	EPrints, managed by CoSector University of London
Wrexham University	https://wrexham.repository.guildhe.ac.uk/	500 items	GuildHE shared service platform, managed by CoSector University of London

2.3 Engagement with NHS Wales

Welsh universities have a range of levels of interaction with NHS Wales

The eight Welsh universities have a range of levels of interaction and engagement with NHS Wales. Some have very limited engagement with NHS Wales, due to not having relevant subject coverage. In other cases, there are extensive and deep connections based on numerous research collaborations. Strong examples of collaboration between academia and NHS Wales include the [Secure Anonymised Information Linkage \(SAIL\) databank](#) which was mentioned by one interviewee as an example of storing NHS data (sensitive anonymised data).

There are also significant numbers of staff with dual affiliations, where people have roles both in NHS Wales and in a university. However, whilst there are some areas of overlapping interest and activity, there is limited scope for collaboration in relation to purchasing or procurement of resources, such as shared publisher deals at organisation level between universities and NHS Wales.

“There are collaborative things that are born of the discipline because they need people in practice to drive the research. I think there are barriers because of the publication models. Publishers aren't very good at letting people do joint purchasing.” – Librarian, HE Wales

2.4 Existing University Presses in Wales

Wales has two University Presses, which both offer some element of Diamond OA publishing

There are currently two University Presses in Wales, [Cardiff University Press](#) and the [University of Wales Press](#). Additionally, one other university hosts two OA journals and another university is in the process of launching an in-house student research journal.

The two University Presses have quite distinct audiences:

- Cardiff University Press publishes work by authors with an affiliation to the University. Publications include monographs and journals. The Press is managed within the University Library and is funded by the University. Its journal publications include the [British Student Doctor Journal](#) (case study 1 below).
- The University of Wales Press publishes works from and about Wales, focusing on Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences. It is a not-for-profit academic press and publishes around 50 monographs a year as well as journals. Although it does not publish medical or health and care works, it does publish a Diamond OA journal at the interface of academia and practice in relation to educational research in the [Wales Journal of Education](#). This is published with the support of the Welsh Government (case study 2 below).

Case study 1: [British Student Doctor Journal](#), Cardiff University Press

Founded in 2016 by two medical students at Cardiff University and supported by the Academy of Medical Educators as its official journal, the [British Student Doctor Journal \(BSDJ\)](#) is a peer-reviewed OA journal managed by medical students and resident doctors. Although it is international in scope, it is primarily aimed at a UK readership.

17 items were published in 2025, including editorials, original research, academic essays as opinion pieces (“discussion starters”) or focusing on a particular aspect of medical education, and correspondence.

The editorial board of the journal are volunteers, as are the peer reviewers.

More broadly, Cardiff University Press was established in 2014 and sits within the University Library where 1 FTE staff supports the activity of the Press. An Editorial Board oversees the Press, and includes academic and student representatives from the University.

Case study 2: [Wales Journal of Education](#), University of Wales Press

The [Wales Journal of Education](#) has been published for nearly 30 years serving the field of educational research methods and methodologies. It was a long-standing prestigious journal which flipped to a Diamond OA model in 2020, supported by the Welsh Government. Published twice a year, articles are published bilingually in both Welsh and English, with no charges for authors or readers.

22 items were published in 2025 (this includes both Welsh and English language versions of articles).

Additionally, “Focus on Practice” articles are published throughout the year, rather than as part of the numbered issues. The journal website also hosts other value-added content, including a practitioner portal and podcasts.

More broadly, the University of Wales Press is a team of 12 people, run as a not-for-profit academic press with a range of funding sources including Medr and the Welsh Government. It outsources translation, proof-reading and copy-editing and partners with the University of Chicago Press for distribution in America, Australia and New Zealand.

3. The current landscape of OA publishing within NHS Wales

This section summarises the current publishing landscape within NHS Wales

NHS Wales benefits from OA publication routes available to co-authors in academic institutions. Where these are not present, levels of OA are noticeably lower – less than half of such outputs from the last ten years are available through OA.

This section also considers the benefits of OA publishing to NHS Wales, types of content which would be suitable for wider sharing, current approaches to recording published outputs from NHS Wales organisations and case studies from other health systems.

3.1 Overview of NHS Wales OA publishing trends 2015-24

There are high levels of co-authorship between NHS Wales and WHELF organisations...

Search results from the Dimensions database show high levels of co-authorship between NHS Wales² and WHELF organisations over the last ten years. Nearly a third of all NHS Wales publications are collaborations involving at least one WHELF co-author and a further 31% of all NHS Wales publications are with “education” (academic) co-authors beyond WHELF.

Where NHS Wales authors co-author publications with academic authors (in WHELF or beyond Wales), the trends of OA publishing compared to closed publications are similar to those observed for WHELF publications described in section 2.1. Overall, numbers of OA publications nearly doubled between 2015 and 2024. However, there is a much more pronounced peak in OA publishing during the pandemic years of 2020-2022, followed by a dip in numbers of OA publications.

OA and closed publication trends for all NHS Wales publications (including those co-authored with academics in WHELF and beyond) are shown in solid lines in Figure 4.

...but where NHS Wales publications do not have academic co-authors, use of OA is much lower

37% of all NHS Wales publications over the last ten years were published without an academic co-author and among these, use of OA publication routes is noticeably lower.

For most of the last decade, most NHS Wales-only publications were closed access, with a brief period during which a majority of publications were published through OA routes between 2020-23.

OA and closed publication trends for NHS Wales publications without academic co-authors are shown in the dashed lines in Figure 4.

² This includes authors giving their organisational affiliation as an NHS Wales Health Board or Trust, or a specific named hospital within NHS Wales.

Figure 4. NHS Wales publications, 2015-24.

NHS Wales publications without academic co-authors have lower proportions of OA use than WHELF publications or the UK average for health-related disciplines

NHS Wales publications without academic co-authors are significantly less likely to be OA, with only 45% of these publications over the last ten years being published through an OA route.

This compares to 71% of WHELF health-related publications, 63% of all WHELF publications, 64% of all UK health-related publications and 59% of all NHS Wales publications (including those co-authored with academics).

Without academic co-authors, use of Green OA is significantly lower in NHS Wales (about half the level of Green OA found where NHS Wales publications have academic co-authors). (Figure 5)

Figure 5. Modes of publication, 2015-24.

Further insights illustrate venue preferences and co-authorship patterns

Elsevier, British Medical Journal and Oxford University Press are the top 3 publishers for NHS Wales publications without academic co-authors. It is noted that NHS Wales has a national read and publish subscription to BMJ Case Reports.

Patterns of co-authorship are illustrated in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Networks of NHS Wales co-authorship, 2015-24.

3.2 Perceived benefits of OA publishing within the NHS

Potential benefits of OA publishing are clearly articulated, including the **opportunity to improve services...**

Interviewees in NHS Wales, Higher Education and those contributing as experts clearly articulated the benefits of OA in NHS Wales.

These include opportunities to improve services to patients, by maximising access to high-quality published evidence and guidance on best practice.

"Open Access aims to support informed decision-making as well as supporting visibility of research undertaken in the Health Board." – Librarian, NHS Wales

"We need information, evidence, evaluation from the work that we do. It will help us design excellent health and social care services to serve the population of Wales." – R&D, NHS Wales

...mitigate the **risks of the lack of sharing**...

There are also risks which potentially arise from a lack of open access or effective sharing of information. For example, if significant reports relating to patient safety, quality and service improvement are not feeding into patient care to the extent they could, there may be a risk of harm to patients.

"It's good practice to share serious incident reports and there is no repository for those things and people could therefore be making the same mistakes." – Wider landscape expert

...**social value arguments**...

There are also strongly articulated social value arguments in favour of Open Access to health information, where there is intrinsic benefit from having free access to the most up-to-date, quality approved information.

"If we talk about collaboration, about values-based healthcare, sharing information in a way that everybody can access it for the common good – it's part of the DNA of the NHS, isn't it?" – R&D, NHS Wales

...and ensuring **access to publications and intellectual property** arising from publicly-funded NHS work

Open Access also enables access to publications arising from work undertaken with public funding within the NHS. Without it, content created by publicly-funded NHS work would need to be purchased back by the NHS in journal subscriptions.

Additionally, publications include key intellectual property developed within the NHS, which is in some cases not being proactively or effectively managed when it is published in closed access publications.

"We're buying content that's produced by the NHS and paying NHS money to be able to access it in the NHS and that doesn't feel quite right in terms of public money." – Wider landscape expert

3.3 Scope for developing an NHS Wales OA policy

There is generally perceived to be low awareness of OA within NHS Wales

There is generally perceived to be low awareness of OA within NHS Wales, although this varies by size of organisation. NHS Wales librarians describe small but growing numbers of enquiries about OA publishing routes, including about availability of funds to cover APCs, approaches to including OA costs in funding applications, requests for codes for BMJ journals with read and publish arrangements, and potential OA venues for publishing research.

There is also a wider context of significant pressures within NHS Wales which means that OA may not be prioritised within organisations: *"not in our top 100 things that we're concerned about"* (R&D, NHS Wales).

...but there is appetite for an NHS Wales OA policy

NHS Wales interviewees generally indicate that their local organisations do not currently have OA policies in place. NHS Wales is not unusual in this respect; of the five nations of the UK and the Republic of Ireland, only the Irish Health Service Executive has an [Open Access publishing statement](#).

However, there is evidence of an appetite for a national NHS Wales policy, with a general consensus that policy set at a national level may be more easily implemented. There is, however, a need to recognise and consider how it would be applied across the diverse organisations within NHS Wales.

"I would welcome a policy on Open Access. It should be an all-Wales approach so that we're consistent across all the Health Boards." – R&D, NHS Wales

There are other initiatives which can inform approaches to developing an NHS Wales OA policy

There are other initiatives which could inform approaches to developing an NHS Wales OA policy. These include the [Digital Health and Care Wales OA policy](#), as well as publishing guidance from Public Health Wales. There is also work underway to develop and implement guidance to improve consistency in NHS Wales authors' use of identity and affiliation descriptions, including through the use of ORCID³.

In England, there is a new [Intellectual Property policy for NHS England](#) which includes one mention of OA as a potential route to disseminate non-commercial NHS outputs.

3.4 Current approaches to recording and sharing outputs

Significant effort and work is already undertaken to monitor and report on NHS Wales publications...

There is already considerable effort and work being undertaken to monitor and report on publications within NHS Wales organisations. This activity is undertaken for the purpose of internal reporting of publications on a regular basis, and to enable libraries to signpost staff to work undertaken by colleagues.

The format in which this information is held includes Excel files, local databases (e.g. Access), listings on an intranet or external webpage, use of Zotero libraries, an Endnote reference library, or saved searches in bibliographic databases such as Medline and CINAHL. In one case, a significant project over two years has been undertaken to populate an internal NHS Wales SharePoint site with details of publications from an NHS Wales organisation dating back to the formation of the current NHS Wales structure in 2009.

³ ORCID (Open Researcher and Contributor ID) is a unique persistent digital identifier available free of charge to researchers. This enables transparent and trustworthy identification of an individual researcher's contributions and affiliations as they engage in research, scholarship and innovation activities.

...however, there are risks with these approaches

There are potential risks with these approaches. These risks include:

- duplication of effort (“reinventing the wheel”);
- creating local systems which are vulnerable to the loss of key expertise;
- reliance on manual sharing (e.g. lists included in annual R&D reports if they are issued); and
- limited opportunities for sharing between organisations.

“All the libraries that are maintaining staff publications records for their Health Boards will search across every database that we have access to in NHS Wales and some of the grey literature ones too. For the large health boards, it's at least a day's work, if not longer.” – Librarian, NHS Wales

3.5 Types of content suitable for OA

A wide range of different types of content were identified as potentially useful to capture and share...

Document and content types which were described as potentially suitable for OA sharing included:

- published works (articles, chapters, monographs, handbooks);
- dissertations;
- grey literature reports arising from research, such as audit reports, case studies, quality improvement reports;
- clinical guidelines;
- strategy documents, annual reports, organisational and policy documents (including organisational documents potentially suitable for routine publication under the Freedom of Information Act);
- HTML reports; and
- plain language summaries.

“The amount of FOI requests [Information Governance] get... I wonder how many of those could be eliminated if we made those kinds of reports openly available.” – Librarian, NHS Wales

“There's a lot of report output from the NHS that it would be valuable to see more accessible: quality improvement reports and other types of document which it would be nice to see in the public domain. It's about making the right kind of content available to everyone in the right kind of format... the manual that describes how you can reconfigure a service, where does that sit at the moment?” – Wider landscape expert

...although some content would benefit from sharing within NHS Wales, but would not be suitable for public access

However, there are also some documents for which NHS Wales sharing would be helpful, but which would not be suitable for public access. There would need to be “managed access” via suitable authentication systems to ensure that the right content was visible to the right people.

In some cases, concerns about suitable levels of access to content would be justified by the sensitivity of relevant material. In other cases, NHS organisations may be more protective of content than would appear justified or proportionate, including where there may be expectations of system-wide sharing of information.

“I have a feeling that the organisation would be a bit worried about sharing sensitive and even some things that I don't even consider sensitive, they would be quite hesitant to share, because sometimes they do worry about reputational issues or things being misinterpreted or being picked up by the press and taken out of context.” - NHS Wales

3.6 Examples from other health systems

Three case studies

This section presents three case studies from Ireland, England and Scotland, illustrating alternative approaches to managing publications from health services:

- Case study 3 describes [Lenus.ie](#), Ireland's OA health research repository.
- Case study 4 describes [EMER](#), the East Midlands Evidence Repository.
- Case study 5 describes [Public Health Scotland's COVID-19 Research Repository](#).

All three of these examples are from geographic areas which are bigger than Wales in terms of population⁴ but show how institutional repositories focusing on health and care can be effectively implemented within a region or nation. Lenus is the most established of these repositories as well as the largest by a very considerable margin.

Case study 3: Lenus

[Lenus.ie](#) is Ireland's OA health research repository and began as a digital archive for the health service in 2009, involving digitising grey literature and reports from within health service organisations. Since 2013, health service staff have also been encouraged to use it as a repository for OA journal articles, becoming a go-to resource for Irish health research. Items are also harvested from other Irish institutional repositories, and from bodies which publish grey literature, such as annual inspection reports.

There are also broader initiatives to encourage OA publishing including recognition through the annual HSE OA research awards.

The system is maintained by one member of staff and currently has over 34,000 items.

⁴ According to the UK's [Office of National Statistics mid-year estimates for 2024](#), Wales had a population of 3.2m, Scotland's population was 5.5m and the East Midlands had a population of 5m (note that EMER only covers a subset of counties included in the formal definition of the region which also includes Lincolnshire). The Republic of Ireland's population was estimated to be 5.4m in 2024 ([Central Statistics Office](#)).

Figure 7 shows how use of Lenus has increased over time, based on year of publication, with a peak in numbers of items added to the repository during the pandemic. It is unclear what contributed to the earlier peak in publications in 2017, although it seems that a large number of inspection reports from the Health Information and Quality Authority were added to the repository in that year.

Figure 7. Numbers of items in Lenus by publication year (2015-24).

Case study 4: EMER

EMER is the East Midlands Evidence Repository, the official institutional research repository for twelve NHS organisations across the East Midlands, covering Derbyshire, Leicestershire, Northamptonshire and Nottinghamshire.

It aims to make NHS research from the participating organisations more visible and discoverable by capturing, storing and preserving the research outputs and making it accessible, with full-text content provided wherever possible.

The system currently holds just over 9,500 items and saw almost 400 new publications deposited in the 2025 calendar year.

Case study 5: Public Health Scotland: COVID-19 Research Repository

Public Health Scotland: COVID-19 Research Repository was created with 16 partners (including Scottish Universities) to provide access to Scottish COVID-19 research for an international audience. Its objectives are to:

- "make research easier to find;
- raise awareness of Scottish research;
- track, understand and report on the impact of this work;
- reduce duplication of effort;
- encourage a collaborative, cross-sectoral approach to COVID-19 research in Scotland;
- provide full-text open access to research wherever possible; and
- ensure permanent preservation of PHS research"

The repository currently holds just over 7,600 items.

4. Stakeholder appetites for increasing OA publishing in this field

There is significant appetite for increasing OA publishing in NHS Wales

There is significant appetite for increasing OA publishing in NHS Wales, supported by experiences of previous initiatives and existing trust between WHELF members and the NHS. This section also outlines the importance of implementing new systems and approaches at an appropriate level.

There is appetite for potential Diamond OA publishing by NHS Wales, although there is also an acknowledgment of the challenges and limitations of this model in the context of current resource constraints in the NHS and Higher Education.

4.1 Previous initiatives, trust and benefits of collaboration

Different drivers and potential benefits for NHS Wales and WHELF

There are different drivers for WHELF and NHS Wales for exploring alternative routes to growing the amount of OA publishing, and it is likely that any initiatives focusing on health and care publications would be significantly more beneficial for NHS Wales in the short term, but could have benefits for WHELF institution in the medium to longer term.

There is strong articulation of the value of collaborative approaches to OA

There is a strong positive articulation of the value of collaborative approaches to OA, from both NHS Wales and university participants. Financial pressures in HE are contributing to interest in opportunities to move away from the transformative agreement initiatives, with suggestions that this may provide an opportunity for a paradigm shift.

“There’s a very good history of collaboration between Welsh universities and between university libraries and their NHS counterparts. ... my reflection is that Wales is the right size for that kind of collaborative approach to succeed: there are enough people that you can keep everybody together and not too many that it breaks down” – Librarian, HE Wales

There is a climate of trust amongst WHELF and NHS Wales libraries

More generally, there is a favourable climate of trust between WHELF institutions and with NHS Wales.

This is based on substantial previous collaborations, such as the implementation of a joint Library Management System (LMS) within WHELF and NHS Wales libraries which came into operation in 2016.

“In Wales, the relationships exist, because of the shared LMS which extends to NHS libraries. So we all know one another – one of the key things around sharing activity is around trust and I think that already exists.” – Librarian, HE Wales

DHCW's open access policy and repository as a basis for development

DHCW has led on developing an open access policy and implementing a repository for DHCW funded publications. The open access policy was soft-launched in spring 2024, and launched publicly in 2025. Its development was underpinned by wider discussions across NHS Wales about the potential for a system-wide open access policy. Evaluation of the DHCW OA policy over the coming year or two (it is due for review in 2027) can inform future scope for developing an NHS Wales OA policy.

The current small scale of the DHCW repository (31 items as of January 2026) has enabled straightforward, low-cost implementation and leaves open a full range of options for re-procurement, which is due in autumn 2026. This could include procurement of a system which could be scaled up to cover other NHS Wales organisations over time.

"[There is potential to] scale up eventually... pretty much all of the repositories will allow this. [Another organisation] could potentially procure the same system and have a discovery layer over the top that would surface everything from those organisations." –

Librarian, NHS Wales

There are also opportunities for informing developments with a wider geographic scope

Wider geographic scope may also be an alternative way to mitigate the perceived lack of volume of publishing within Wales (see section 4.2 below). Opportunities for collaborative action could exist between the five nations of Wales, Scotland, Northern Ireland, England (or some English regions) and the Republic of Ireland. The Five Nations group of health service library leads from England, Northern Ireland, Ireland, Scotland and Wales already work closely together to find solutions to issues and to share resources and ideas. Whilst the resourcing or delivery of formal joint initiatives between the five health systems may not be possible, there is scope for developing co-ordinated approaches to policy and practice in UK and Irish healthcare libraries.⁵

4.2 Opportunities to increase volume of outputs

Scope to increase volume of publication in Wales

There is a perception of scope for increasing the volume of outputs in Wales. In higher education, this is manifested in the very different scales of published outputs from institutions of differing research intensity.

In NHS Wales, there are clear indications of people being put off publishing research because of the high cost of APCs, or because they are not aware of potential routes for publishing their work. Improving visibility of OA options and enabling easy and straightforward OA routes could make publication easier for these NHS Wales staff.

In other cases, publications may exist, but not be captured or surfaced. This may be particularly the case where NHS Wales staff have published without an academic affiliation

⁵ Goring et al (2023) provides an example of a joint research project on e-book use in healthcare libraries informing action in individual nations and development of shared information, guidance and organisation of events.

or collaborator. This is a gap which could be filled – for example, through use of Green OA – in a way which would raise the profile of NHS Wales research.

Steps towards encouraging publications from NHS Wales staff could include introducing and using an OA policy. This could incorporate guidance on consistent identity and affiliation descriptions, use of ORCID and appropriate rights retention⁶ and licensing, similar to the OA policy introduced by DHCW.

“It’s not necessarily research for general interest, it’s research to make the ward run better or to improve nursing training, but it would be good to publish to pass on what you found out to others”. – Librarian, NHS Wales

Scope for targeted approaches to professional groups

There is also scope to develop approaches targeted at specific staff groups or professions. This could recognise, for example, that whilst established medical academics are most likely to publish with university partners, early or mid-career medics, nurses, AHPs and social care practitioners may particularly value an easy-to-use local publication route.

“There would be benefits for sharing information between Health Boards and learning from each other in terms of best practise.” – NHS Wales

OA and potential to reach wider audiences

There is also opportunity to emphasise the benefits of OA publishing in terms of potential to reach a wider audience. There is evidence that publishing pre-prints leads to more citations⁷. Emphasising this improved visibility and use of pre-prints could help to encourage people to use OA routes to publication.

There is a need to recognise inequity in publishing between sectors and professions

There is a need to recognise the difference between the publishing volume and infrastructure in academic settings compared to an NHS setting. There are also significant differences between publication practices and volumes between medical, nursing and care and social care professions. Understanding the current inequities in publishing opportunities and practices between these sectors should inform the development of more equitable approaches to alternative publishing models.

“The further away from an academic setting to an NHS or even further into the health and care system and social care side of things, the further away from entities that can provide support for publishing either in talking you through the process, or payment of publishing

⁶ Rights retention enables authors to exercise the rights they have on their manuscripts to deposit a copy of the Author Accepted Manuscript (AAM) in a repository on publication and provide open access to it. [Coalition-S provides more information about this approach on its website.](#)

⁷ Colavizza et al (2024) suggests “that early release of preprints is associated with a significant citation advantage of approximately 20.2%”.

fees. So going from the hard academic end right way through to supporting local government, there's inequity. Whatever solution's put together, it's got to be more equitable than the status quo." – Wider landscape expert

4.3 Implementation needs to sit at the appropriate level

There is general support for the idea of collaboration in this area...

There is support for the idea of collaboration in the area of OA across Wales, with a number of interviewees voicing a sense that Wales is the right size and that NHS Wales may be sufficiently centralised to make effective collaboration feasible.

Previous collaborations in the area of OA have been explored, including the idea of a shared repository for all Welsh research. In the early 2000s the DSpace system was in use across Welsh universities and a joint repository was considered then, however these systems have since diverged, starting before the 2014 Research Excellence Framework (REF). There were subsequent conversations about an all-Wales repository before the COVID-19 pandemic, but these have not progressed further.

The challenge with the idea of an all-Wales HE repository appeared to be in agreeing what the shape and scope of this repository would be. There does seem to be continuing interest in this as a potential future avenue for development within Welsh higher education institutions. Examples of successful region-wide research infrastructures from other countries include [FRIS – Flanders repository](#) and the [Netherlands Research Portal](#). The Netherlands Research Portal includes research output associated with Dutch hospitals. Elsevier Pure – in use by half of Welsh HEIs – also provides options for [region-wide implementations](#).

"If it's institutional to the extent that no one else in the health and care system can access it, that's quite limiting... we need to get better at sharing the learning and understanding and research rather than limiting it to a particular sector or a particular organisation." – R&D, NHS Wales

...whilst identifying the appropriate balance in resource and autonomy

There is a need for implementation at the appropriate level to effectively balance the benefits of reducing duplication of effort, with proportionate contributions from each organisation and preservation of local autonomy. This was articulated by one participant as "national principles, locally applied".

Within the NHS, this would mean providing a platform suitable for national adoption or integration, whilst enabling individual Health Boards to choose the extent of their participation and to manage their own content. This would also need to reflect the different size and shape of NHS Wales organisations.

"A more joined-up approach would make a lot of sense rather than replicating activity. But I think [the question] would be the finances of it and the balance of outputs from one

organisation versus another and the relative contribution to the costs.” - Academic, HE Wales

There may be risks of siloing information by discipline or sector

There are also some issues with potential for siloing information in an approach which focuses only on NHS Wales research. Reflecting on previous discussions about the idea of a repository for all Welsh research, there is some perception that covering all subject areas in one place would better enable cross-fertilisation.

On the other hand, there is also a view expressed that an NHS Wales repository could encourage further developments towards wider use of combined repositories. Given the challenging financial circumstances for higher education, the likelihood of a Wales-wide HE-based research repository appears to be low in the medium term. Having an NHS Wales repository would provide a resource offering value on its own terms, and as a potential component in any future initiatives for repository integration in Wales.

“This could be great as a starter for something bigger that we need to move to, or possibly this could be a disincentive: saying health has gone that way, [everything else] will go [a different] way.” – Librarian, HE Wales

4.4 Appetites for Diamond OA

There is support for the idea of Diamond OA as a route to increasing NHS Wales OA publishing

Amongst HE interviewees, there is a broad articulation of a perception of Diamond OA as an “ideal” or “utopian” model for OA publishing which could avoid or mitigate some of the challenges of Gold or Green OA.

There is also support for the idea of Diamond OA as a route to increasing NHS Wales OA publishing. This could particularly benefit NHS Wales staff who would like to be able to publish, but are deterred by the cost of APCs, and staff who undertake small research projects which could make a difference to patient care and would benefit from wider dissemination.

As one participant noted, a Diamond OA publication would enable NHS Wales to “put its own stamp to fantastic research being done in Wales”.

Diamond OA is a growing feature of medical publishing

There is particular scope for Diamond OA journals in the medical and health fields, where journals in these fields make up a significant minority of publications⁸.

⁸ An OA expert interviewee estimated this as 20% of Diamond OA journals. A subject search in the [Directory of Open Access Journals \(DOAJ\)](#) for journals which do not charge APCs in the subject area of medicine returned 2,206 journal titles, out of a total of 14,074 journals which do not charge APCs. This suggests that 16% of DOAJ indexed Diamond OA journals are in the medical subject area.

There are particularly prestigious and well-established examples of journals which have flipped from being published in traditional ways to being entirely Diamond. Two examples include:

- The *Swiss Medical Weekly*, first published as a traditional journal in 1871. The journal is the official publication of four Swiss medical associations and is funded by 30+ Swiss institutions (including the Swiss Government). In 2025, 165 items were published.
- The *Irish Medical Journal*, first published as a traditional journal in 1867. The journal is the official publication of the Irish Medical Organisation. In 2025, 163 items were published.

“The estimate we have is about 20% of Diamond Open Access journals are medical journals, and specifically medical journals oriented towards practitioners, to translate the knowledge of medical insights into articles for practitioners which they can access without having to buy a subscription.” – Wider landscape expert

Opportunities for bilingual publication

Diamond OA is also hospitable to multilingual publishing. Compared to Gold OA journals, where the vast majority of titles are in English only, there is more linguistic diversity in Diamond journals. Local demand and interest in publishing in languages other than English can be more easily met by establishing a low-cost Diamond OA journal supported by a particular linguistic community, than by changing established practices in international publishing, where English-language publications have largely dominated since the mid-twentieth century.

The potential for bilingual publication in Welsh and English also adds a unique dimension both as a potential venue for Welsh language outputs without current publication routes and for public access to Welsh language material. Options for bilingual publication would include either publishing abstracts or whole articles in translation.

“96% of Gold Open Access journals are English only, while in fact all the linguistic diversity you find on the diamond side... We should really encourage the idea that it's normal to publish in multiple languages and that there is no exclusion, that people should use the language of their choice and the language their readers are familiar with.” – Wider landscape expert

There is a need for a pragmatic approach to identifying the audience and setting clear boundaries to the publication

A key determinant of potential options for development would be the wider community's appetite for an NHS Wales approach to OA publishing, including whether there is there sufficiently high-level support from a funder or from the wider community, such as professional associations representing NHS Wales staff and those involved in teaching and educating health and care professionals.

This in turn would feed into knowing who the target audience would be for a potential Diamond publication, such as an OA journal, ensuring that there is clarity about who it is for and, informing decisions about how it would be presented. It would also help to consider whether there is a niche which NHS Wales could fill in a distinctive way.

Participants suggested possible areas of interest such as community healthcare, rural health services, healthcare in post-industrial settings, social care or sharing of policy and practice within NHS institutions.

Setting clear, realistic and pragmatic boundaries around the scope of an NHS Wales publication could cover would maximise potential for success.

“Diamond Open Access Publishing has to find its place and do what it can within the limitations that already exist. There is an element of reality check that people have to set parameters around Diamond Open Access publishing. We can't do everything, but we can make good inroads in X area – pick that area and set targets that are realistic.” - Wider landscape expert

There is some scepticism about the potential for Diamond to replace Gold OA

There is also some scepticism about the potential for Diamond to replace Gold, with a particular focus on funding constraints. Within universities, there is a perception of likely gradual attrition on uptake of big deals as individual institutions find them increasingly difficult to afford. However, this does not currently seem to be matched by appetite for an alternative model, or funding to sustain it.

“Diamond Open Access is all about being community-owned but you can't make something sustainable unless there's proper funding in place” – Wider landscape expert

Need to articulate benefits for institutions and funders

A common theme is that institutions cannot afford “altruistic” support of Diamond – there needs to be a clear indication of how it could save money or show return on investment. This can include controlling costs, providing greater resilience through shared service approaches and improving visibility for research outputs.

Funders are also facing pressure with budgets and there are opportunities to present alternative models of OA publishing as ways to maximise funder impact.

“The Diamond Open Access dream is probably more of a mirage, for all the enthusiasm behind it. Somebody has to pay and the usual question arises: if the author's not paying and their institution is not paying, who is?” – Academic, HE Wales

Quality assurance is key

Quality assurance is a key requirement for publishing in health and care fields, where accuracy is particularly important. Quality assurance includes editorial standards and peer-review process to ensure the quality of the content, as well as quality of the production of the final published outputs.

Quality is also linked to the choice of editorial board members, with potential for high profile well-respected experts in the relevant field to add credibility to the publication.

One participant noted the value of quality over quantity – for example, starting with a single journal and then potentially scaling up from that.

“If a Diamond journal is set up, to get the best research it will have to develop a reputation and have a really prestigious editorial board and link it into recognition of clinicians and academic staff.” – Academic, HE Wales

5. Options analysis

This section describes four options for consideration

Although the most immediate benefit in developing OA routes for NHS Wales staff would be to the NHS, there would be scope over time to combine or integrate NHS Wales OA approaches with those in WHELF institutions. Similarly, new OA publications aimed primarily at NHS staff could also publish work by academics and students at WHELF institutions.

This section presents four options for consideration:

- Option 1: do nothing
- Option 2: implement an NHS Wales repository
- Option 3: pilot a Diamond OA Journal
- Option 4: establish a Diamond OA Press

Options 2-4 are summarised in Figure 8, with red (weaker) – amber (moderate) – green (stronger) indications of key aspects of each option. These colour codes are based on relative assessment for each of the criteria, which are explored in more detail in the narrative sections describing each option in sections 5.2-5.4 below. Appendix C describes resources which provide guidance and information about relevant standards, systems and approaches for implementing a repository or for open access publishing.

Figure 8. Summary of options 2-4.

Criteria	NHS Wales repository	Diamond OA Journal	Diamond OA Press
Amount of OA facilitated: <i>Quantity of items made accessible</i>	Green	Yellow	Yellow
Potential for integration: <i>Opportunity to connect with other systems</i>	Green	Yellow	Yellow
Scalable: <i>Options for future expansion of coverage</i>	Green	Yellow	Yellow
Sustainable: <i>Potential for long-term continuation</i>	Green	Yellow	Red
Feasibility: <i>Overall viability, including use of existing capacity & processes</i>	Green	Yellow	Red
Technical feasibility: <i>Viability of systems set-up and maintenance</i>	Green	Green	Yellow
Risks: <i>Likelihood and severity of potential risks</i>	Green	Yellow	Red
Admin burden: <i>Complexity and amount of administration</i>	Yellow	Yellow	Red
Complexity of governance: <i>Number of stakeholders & split of responsibility</i>	Green	Yellow	Red
Quality oversight: <i>Expert input into quality assurance (e.g. editorial roles)</i>	Yellow	Green	Green
Finance: <i>Overall cost including staff time, systems and maintenance</i>	Green	Yellow	Red
Cost vs value: <i>Likely return in value output from investment spent</i>	Green	Yellow	Yellow
Staff time: <i>Number of staff and level of expertise required</i>	Yellow	Yellow	Red

Key – colour coding indicates that for each of the criteria, each option is relatively:

Stronger	Moderate	Weaker
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5.1 Option 1: do nothing

Overview

This option would continue current approaches to publishing outputs and managing publications from the interface of health and academia.

Potentially this would assume that WHELF organisations continue to prioritise Gold and Green OA routes for publishing in health and care. Wales's two University Presses would continue to focus mostly on subjects beyond health and care

This would also assume that academic co-authorship of individual articles would be the main route to OA publication for the majority of outputs from NHS Wales.

Benefits and disadvantages

Benefits of this approach would include no additional need for financial resource to support a new initiative.

Disadvantages of this approach would be a missed opportunity to improve efficiency, reduce duplication of effort and explore innovative collaborative approaches to publishing.

Risks

The risks are that there would continue to be under-representation of OA publication routes amongst NHS Wales staff with no co-authors in academia and that opportunities to improve and enhance patient care and service delivery through wider dissemination of research, good practice and quality improvement outputs would be missed.

For WHELF organisations there is a risk that an opportunity to pilot an innovative collaborative approach to publishing would be missed, and that this might reduce potential for exploring alternative OA models in future.

5.2 Option 2: implement an NHS Wales repository

Overview

This option would develop a repository infrastructure for NHS Wales. This would enable Green OA of peer-reviewed content and would also facilitate the surfacing of grey literature produced within NHS Wales, such as quality improvement reports and organisational strategies.

Benefits and disadvantages

Benefits of this approach are that a repository would provide a low-cost route to OA publication from NHS Wales staff, as well as enabling NHS Wales to track and manage publications and other outputs from the health service. A repository would enable wider dissemination of outputs relevant to patient care and service quality, which could also be integrated with the wider set of information resources available via the NHS Wales e-Library.

Disadvantages would include additional financial costs and staff time to populate a repository and then to manage it on an ongoing basis.

Risks

Risks of this approach would include:

- Sustainability over time would be dependent on financial resource and staffing.

- Repositories do not provide editorial, review or quality assurance, and inclusion and exclusion criteria would need to be carefully defined to ensure relevance and credibility.
- Potential disclosure of sensitive information, if appropriate access controls are not appropriately implemented.

Strategy and feasibility

Implementation of a repository would be underpinned strategically through an NHS Wales-wide OA policy.

The feasibility of this option appears to be high, considering both the work already undertaken within individual libraries and Health Boards to track local publications, and the opportunity to learn from experiences of repository management within WHELF organisations.

As a guide to the time required to establish a repository, [AMBER – Ambulance Research Repository](#) took one year from inception to completion, including a three-year backfilling of earlier literature (covering 2017-2019). This repository now includes just over 2,000 items.

The scope and timeframe to be covered by the NHS Wales repository would need careful consideration. Table 2 indicates the relative number of publications in Dimensions associated with NHS Wales, with and without academic co-authors over the last ten years and gives some idea of the potential scale of items which could be added to a repository. A shorter timeframe could focus on publications since 2020, or since reorganisations of some NHS Wales Health Boards in 2018-19.

There would also be a rationale for including a longer timeframe, if resources permit, going back to the formation of many current NHS Wales structures in 2009, or potentially even earlier.

Table 2. Numbers of publications from NHS Wales including / excluding academic co-authors, 2015-24

Publications including/excluding academic co-authors	No. publications
NHS Wales (including academic co-authors)	15,493
NHS Wales (no academic co-authors)	5,657

Governance

A repository would need to meet the needs of the broad range of diverse organisations and staff groups within NHS Wales. A potential governance structure would include representatives from all NHS Wales Health Boards and Trusts, as well as potential advisory involvement from key WHELF contacts, sharing expertise and providing advice and guidance about repository management. This should also include both library and research and development stakeholders, and ideally would be chaired by a senior roleholder with experience of NHS and academic organisations. Slightly different approaches to governance could be adopted in the project set-up phase and subsequently in the routine management of the repository once it has been implemented.

People

In addition to the people involved in governance, 1 FTE staff would be suggested as proportionate resource for implementing the repository. Depending on the scale of backfilling of data, the extent to which this can be automated and also any local or central

need for digitisation of documents there might be need for additional fractional FTE to support initial implementation.

Training of local NHS Wales library and R&D staff to use and maintain the repository in their local organisations would also be needed.

Systems

A full procurement exercise would be needed to identify the preferred provider of a repository platform. However, **DSpace** is used for the Lenus, EMER and AMBER repositories. **EPrints** is used for the DHCW Research and Knowledge Repository.

Given the noted potential for the repository to be used both for published materials suitable for open access by the public, and value of system-wide sharing of more sensitive documents, system options for access control, authentication and integration with other NHS Wales e-Library resources should be explored.

The repository should also enable automated harvesting of relevant records from other Welsh repositories – as is done by Lenus in Ireland.

Finance

The main financial cost would be in staff time to implement and maintain the repository. There may be additional costs for software and service providers. This would include costs for hosting and maintenance (software updates, site security, management of access permissions and authentication). EMER, AMBER and Lenus use **Atmire** as their repository service provider – this provides a range of pricing options, based on the level service and customisation required.

5.3 Option 3: pilot a Diamond OA journal

Overview

This option would pilot one Diamond OA journal, primarily aimed at staff within NHS Wales, but which could also include publications from academics and students within WHELF institutions. This would enable Diamond OA publication of a range of content types including peer-reviewed content. This would rely on community support in terms of interest from potential authors, professional and academic reviewers and editors.

Useful resources to support this approach include the **OA journals toolkit** and the **Diamond OA Standard**.

Benefits and disadvantages

Benefits of this approach are that a pilot Diamond OA journal would provide a low-cost route to OA publication for NHS Wales staff and for academics and students in WHELF institutions, including those who would otherwise be deterred by APC charges, and would increase dissemination of publications relevant to patient care and service quality in Wales. It would provide an opportunity to test the wider feasibility of and appetite for Diamond OA publishing within NHS Wales and at the interface with health and care. It could also provide an opportunity to explore possible collaborations or partnerships with Wales's two university presses. There is also an opportunity to facilitate bilingual publishing in both Welsh and English from within NHS Wales.

Disadvantages would include additional financial costs and staff time to set up and then to manage it on an ongoing basis, as well as volunteer time to carry out peer review and editorial activities.

Risks

Risks of this approach include:

- Scope and audience for the journal are mismatched, contributing to low levels of interest in publishing in the journal.
- Lack of willingness or ability to engage with the journal from relevant NHS Wales staff, academics in relevant subject areas within WHELF institutions or wider stakeholders.
- Insufficient expertise or leadership in the editorial board, leading to concerns about credibility and quality.

Strategy and feasibility

Implementation of a Diamond OA journal pilot would be underpinned strategically through an NHS Wales wide OA policy.

The feasibility of this option appears to be moderate, providing that the scope of the journal is well-defined and pitched to maximise engagement with potential NHS Wales authors. There is currently some ambiguity and lack of clarity around what this scope might be.

Other examples of Diamond OA journals include the [Open Health Research Ireland Network \(OHRIN\) plans to develop a Diamond OA journal](#) for health and social care practitioners, hosted at Trinity College Dublin. Existing journals and platforms frame their scope in a variety of different ways, including:

- Funder-based (Wellcome Open, NIHR Open Research);
- Specialty-focused (especially in medical journals);
- Domain or profession-specific (British Journal of Nursing);
- Format-specific (BMJ Case Reports); and
- Activity and outcome specific – such as the healthcare improvement focus of BMJ Open Quality.

There is both distinctiveness and strength in the NHS Wales brand and ideas for the potential scope of the journal included:

- Journal of Health, Care and Social Care – covering multidisciplinary fields and also enabling third sector partners in social care to submit articles. However, a challenge to this approach was noted to be managing peer review for such a wide-ranging title, potentially relevant to all staff groups;
- Rural and distributed healthcare; or
- health and social care post-deindustrialisation;

Other challenges to feasibility would include identifying potential 10-20 people willing to volunteer in peer review or editorial roles.

Governance

Governance for the pilot project would ideally include representation from the NHS Wales Health Boards and Trusts, as well as from key WHELF contacts. Unlike the repository option, which would be primarily led by NHS Wales, there would need to be more active engagement from academics and partners in WHELF institutions. This steering group would explore levels of interest in a potential pilot publication and identify a preferred area of focus for the journal, ideally in consultation with professional associations.

Governance for the journal itself would sit with an editorial board, ideally with a highly regarded and credible lead editor, who could mobilise interest and potential publications, connecting with the NHS Wales community to build the profile of the journal. Establishing

a credible editorial board would be a key milestone for the pilot project; without a suitably qualified and committed editorial board the pilot should not proceed.

Once the editorial board is established, peer reviewers would also need to be recruited.

People

In addition to the voluntary time offered by members of the editorial board and peer reviewers, operational management of a Diamond OA journal would need between 0.5 FTE – 2.0 FTE to operate successfully. It would be possible for responsibilities for a Diamond OA journal to be combined with those for a repository, and for staff to manage both within the same organisational team.

Systems

A full assessment of publishing workflow systems should be made. Options include Open Journal Systems, Janeway and Ubiquity. There may be additional services needed, such as hosting arrangements for the relevant publishing platform. Hosting arrangements could potentially be combined with those for a repository.

Finance

The main cost would be for staff time, including salary and on-costs. This could be managed efficiently if responsibilities were combined with those for the repository. Diamond OA publishing platforms tend to be no or low cost although these would require hosting and maintenance, similar to repository software. There may be additional costs for any outsourced publishing processes, such as translation of articles.

5.4 Option 4: establish a Diamond OA Press

Overview

This option aims to develop a suite of Diamond OA journals and a route for publishing monographs primarily for staff within NHS Wales. But which could also include publications from academics and students within WHELF institutions. This would enable Diamond OA publication of a range of content types including peer-reviewed content.

A useful source of additional information about quality guidelines is the [Association of University Presses](#).

Benefits and disadvantages

Benefits of this approach are that a Diamond OA Press would provide a low-cost route to OA publication for NHS Wales staff and academics and students within WHELF institutions, including those who would otherwise be deterred by APC charges, and would increase dissemination of publications relevant to patient care and service quality in Wales. It may also provide an opportunity to explore possible collaborations or partnerships with Wales's two existing university presses. There is also an opportunity to facilitate bilingual publishing in both Welsh and English from within NHS Wales. There may also be opportunities to diversify content types available, such as multi-part handbooks or guidelines.

Disadvantages would include additional financial costs and staff time to set up and then to manage it on an ongoing basis, as well as volunteer time to carry out peer review and editorial activities.

Risks

Risks of this approach include:

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- Larger-scale financial commitment without a proven audience;
- Unintended consequences within the context of Wales' wider OA publishing landscape, including relating to its two university presses, unless there was a clear collaborative approach to involving these;
- Lack of willingness or ability to engage with the Press from relevant NHS Wales staff or wider stakeholders; and
- Insufficient expertise or leadership in the editorial board, leading to concerns about credibility and quality.

Strategy and feasibility

Implementation of a Diamond OA press would be underpinned strategically through an NHS Wales wide OA policy.

The feasibility of this option appears to be low, without a proven audience for an NHS Wales Diamond OA Press, but this may change if there were strong evidence of interest and success from the Diamond OA journal pilot.

As with the Diamond OA journal pilot, there would be potential challenges to feasibility relating to identifying potential people willing to volunteer in peer review or editorial roles. Viability would be based on establishing reputation and prestige.

Governance

Governance for the pilot project would ideally include representation from the NHS Wales Health Boards and Trusts, as well as from key WHELF contacts.

Scottish Universities Press (SUP) is an example of an OA publisher, set up as an independent organisation as a Community Interest Company (CIC). It has focused on publishing monographs but in **January 2026 announced that it would also be publishing journals**, inviting expressions of interest from existing journals seeking to migrate to SUP within six months. They will trial this approach with one journal initially, to be followed by two further journals after completion of the pilot. Management of SUP is democratic and made up by the universities which support it financially.

There would also be one or more editorial board members, ideally with a highly regarding and credible lead editor, who could mobilise interest and potential publications, connecting with the NHS Wales community to build the profile of the Press.

People

In addition to people involved in governance, around 1FTE – 2FTE would be needed to manage the operational aspects of the press.

Systems

A full assessment of publishing workflow systems should be made. Options include Open Journal Systems, Janeway and Ubiquity. There may be additional services needed, such as hosting arrangements for the relevant publishing platform.

Finance

Whilst publishing of Diamond OA journals would be relatively low cost beyond staff time (including salary and on-costs), costs of publishing monographs are significantly higher. For example, SUP charges Book Publication charges of between £3.5k-£5.5k depending on length. SUP is funded by subscriptions from each of its members.

6. Conclusions and recommendations

6.1 Conclusions

A challenging landscape for OA publishing This project has explored the landscape of OA publishing in WHELF and in NHS Wales and describes the challenges in both sectors. There is a clear appetite for increasing the levels of OA publishing in Wales. There is a substantial infrastructure in place to support OA through repositories in Welsh HEIs and the country also benefits from two University Presses, although these do not currently have a significant volume of publications in the health and care subject areas

Four options are considered Although the most immediate benefit in developing OA routes for NHS Wales staff would be to the NHS, there would be scope over time to combine or integrate NHS Wales OA approaches with those in WHELF institutions. Similarly, new OA publications aimed primarily at NHS staff could also publish work by academics and students at WHELF institutions.

We present an options analysis describing four potential approaches:

- Option 1: do nothing
- Option 2: implement an NHS Wales repository
- Option 3: pilot a Diamond OA Journal
- Option 4: establish a Diamond OA Press

6.2 Recommendations

We make eight recommendations for taking this work forward

We recommend the following steps as **enabling work**, which would primarily be undertaken by NHS Wales:

1. Continue with ongoing work to make affiliation and identity citing more consistent;
2. Develop and implement NHS Wales OA policy (based on DHCW policy, Public Health Wales (PHW) publishing guidance);
3. Engage with Cardiff University Press and University of Wales Press to explore specific opportunities for potential collaboration or partnership; and
4. Make connections with Open Health Research Ireland Network (OHRIN) regarding their work to develop a Diamond OA journal for health and social care practitioners, hosted at Trinity College Dublin.

There is further work to do to **understand the potential audiences** for a potential Diamond OA journal:

5. Map NHS Wales communities and potential scope of pilot Diamond OA Journal; and
6. Engage with professional associations and / or professional qualification course providers to explore potential scope for an NHS Wales journal.

Based on the findings of this project, we recommend **implementing the following options**:

7. Option 2: Build and manage an NHS Wales repository. This could inform the repository system procurement process to be undertaken by DHCW in autumn 2026:
 - a. Prioritise to maximise potential of Green OA for NHS Wales only;
 - b. Consider how this might support future discussions regarding a cross-Wales (HE and NHS) research repository.
8. Option 3: Pilot Diamond OA journal:
 - a. Trial in one specific area

Implementing these two options would require additional funding and a business case should be submitted to the Welsh Government.

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Declaration of interests

The authors are consultants and researchers working in the field of research and scholarly communication and have provided consultancy services to a subset of the organisations and/or individuals referred to in this project.

This includes previous work with NHS Scotland, Elsevier and Springer Nature.

The authors declare these interests to ensure transparency and to allow readers to critically assess the potential for any bias in the analysis and conclusions.

Appendix A. Glossary

Term	Definition
Article Processing Charge (APC)	A fee charged by some publishers to authors (or their institutions/funders) to make a research article freely available immediately upon publication. APCs vary widely, typically ranging from £500 to £5,000 or more depending on the journal.
Author Accepted Manuscript (AAM)	The version of a research article that has been peer-reviewed and accepted for publication, but has not yet been typeset or formatted by the publisher. Also known as the 'postprint', this version can often be deposited in repositories under Green Open Access policies.
Creative Commons (CC BY)	A standardised licensing framework that allows copyright holders to grant permissions for others to use their work. CC BY (Attribution) is the most open licence, requiring only that the original author is credited, and is the preferred licence for Open Access publications.
Digital Health and Care Wales (DHCW)	A Special Health Authority within NHS Wales responsible for delivering digital services, data, and technology solutions to support health and care across Wales. DHCW has established an Open Access policy and institutional repository for its research outputs.
Diamond Open Access	A publishing model where content is freely available to readers and authors are not charged any fees. Diamond OA journals and presses are typically supported by institutions, learned societies, or funders rather than through author charges.
Embargo period	A specified period following publication during which an article cannot be made freely available in a repository. Embargo periods are set by publishers and typically range from 6 to 24 months, though some funders now require immediate deposit with no embargo.
Green Open Access	A model where authors deposit a version of their work (usually the Author Accepted Manuscript) in an institutional or subject repository, making it freely available either immediately or after an embargo period. The published Version of Record typically remains behind a paywall.
Gold Open Access	A publishing model where articles are made freely available immediately upon publication on the publisher's website, usually under an open licence such as Creative Commons. Gold OA is typically funded through Article Processing Charges, though Diamond OA is a subset that involves no author fees.
Hybrid journal	A subscription-based journal that offers authors the option to pay an APC to make their individual article Open Access whilst the remainder of the journal content remains behind a paywall. Hybrid journals have been criticised for 'double-dipping' (receiving both subscription income and APCs).
NIHR (National Institute for Health and Care Research)	The UK's largest funder of health and care research, which mandates Open Access for publications arising from its funded research.
Open Access	The practice of making research outputs freely available online without access barriers, enabling anyone to read, download, and (depending on the licence) reuse the content. Open Access aims to maximise the dissemination and impact of research findings.

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Preprint	A version of a research paper that is shared publicly before formal peer review and publication in a journal. Preprints are typically deposited on dedicated preprint servers (such as medRxiv for health sciences) to enable rapid dissemination and early feedback.
Read and Publish agreement	A type of contract between an institution (or consortium) and a publisher that combines subscription access ('read') with the ability for affiliated authors to publish Open Access ('publish'), often at no additional cost to the author. These agreements aim to facilitate the transition to Open Access.
Repository	A digital archive used to store, preserve, and provide access to research outputs. Institutional repositories are managed by universities or organisations to collect outputs from their researchers; subject repositories (such as PubMed Central) collect outputs from a specific discipline.
Rights Retention	A strategy whereby authors or their institutions retain certain intellectual property rights to their work, enabling deposit of the Author Accepted Manuscript in a repository regardless of publisher policies. The cOAlition S Rights Retention Strategy is a prominent example.
Scottish Confederation of University and Research Libraries (SCURL)	Membership body that supports service development and improvement across Scotland's university and research libraries through coordination, collaboration and advocacy.
Self-archiving	The practice of authors depositing copies of their own research outputs in a repository to make them freely available. Self-archiving is the primary mechanism for achieving Green Open Access and is often mandated by funders and institutions.
Society of College, National and University Libraries (SCONUL)	The membership organisation representing all university libraries in the UK and Ireland, as well as national libraries and many colleges of higher education. SCONUL advocates on sector-wide issues including Open Access policy and licensing negotiations.
Transitional / Transformative Agreement	A contract between institutions and publishers designed to shift spending from subscription access towards Open Access publishing, with the aim of achieving a fully Open Access model. These time-limited agreements typically combine reading access with publishing rights.
UKRI (UK Research and Innovation)	The UK's national funding body for research and innovation, which mandates Open Access for publications arising from its funded research.
Version of Record (VoR)	The final, published version of an article as it appears in the journal, including all formatting, pagination, and any corrections. The VoR is the definitive version for citation purposes and is typically subject to the publisher's copyright and licensing terms.
Wales Higher Education Libraries Forum (WHELF)	A collaborative consortium of university, NHS, and national libraries in Wales that works to develop shared services, negotiate collective agreements, and advance library provision across the Welsh higher education and health sectors.

Appendix B. Project contributors

The following stakeholders contributed to our project. One further interviewee participated but declined to be listed as a participant until having reviewed the contents of this report.

Name	Organisation	Role
Zara Abberley	Powys Teaching Health Board	Research and Development Manager
Robin Armstrong Viner	Swansea University	Associate Director: Head of Libraries
David Baghurst	NIHR Open Research	Director of Research Programmes NIHR CCF & General Manager NIHR Office for Clinical Research Infrastructure
Karen Caulfield	Hywel Dda UHB	Organisational Development Researcher
Anne Cleves	Velindre University NHS Trust	Library Services Manager
John Dalling	University of Wales Trinity Saint David	Head of Collections
Gillian Daly	Scottish Universities Press	Press Manager
Alisha Davies	Public Health Wales	Head of Research and Evaluation
Jonathan Davies	Aberystwyth University	Resource Discovery Team Leader: Information Security Governance Officer
Amanda Edwards	Powys Teaching Health Board	Assistant Director of Innovation and Improvement
Erika Gavillet	Swansea University	Head of Library & Collection Scholarly Content
Louise Goswami	NHS England	Chief Knowledge Officer
Hugh Griffiths	Cardiff University	Current academic Chair for Cardiff University Press
Lynne Grundy	Betsi Cadwaladar UHB	Associate Director of Research & Innovation
Alison Harding	University of Wales Trinity Saint David	Executive Head of Library and Learning Resources
Mark Hughes	Cardiff Metropolitan University	Head of Libraries
Nia Jenkins	Betsi Cadwaladar UHB	Library Services Manager
Pamela Jones	Betsi Cadwaladar UHB	Library Services Manager
Sarah Lewis	University of Wales Press	Head of Commissioning
Annette Linton	Swansea University	Head of Library & Collection Scholarly Content
Kirsty Little	Public Health Wales	Consultant Lead in Knowledge Mobilisation
Sarah Martin	Cardiff and Vale UHB	Research and Development Manager

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Catherine McLaren	NHS Education for Scotland	Principal Lead – Knowledge Management & Discovery
Isabel O'Kelly	Queen's University Belfast	Open Research Services Manager
Jane Parry	Powys Teaching Health Board	Library Manager
Susan Pope	Aneurin Bevan UHB - Medical Education	Librarian
Tom Powell	Cwm Taf UHB	Head of Innovation
Sara Pritchard	Betsi Cadwaladar UHB	Library Services
Lucy Reid	NHS England	Head of Knowledge and Library Services (Resource Discovery)
Nick Roberts	South Wales	Research Librarian
Johan Rooryck	Diamond Capacity Hub	Co-ordinator
Sam Scoulding	University of Wales Trinity Saint David	Academic Skills Manager
Paul Spencer	Bangor	Pro Vice Chancellor – Research and Innovation
Tracy Stanley	Cardiff University	Director Of University Library Services, Academic and Student Support Services
Rachel Sully	Digital Health and Care Wales	Head of Research and Innovation (Interim) and NHS Wales e-Library and Knowledge Service Manager
Cathy Thornton	Swansea University	Associate Dean - Research, Impact and Innovation
Karin Wahl-Jorgensen	Cardiff University	Dean of Research Environment and Culture
Rhys Whelan	Swansea Bay UHB	Library and Knowledge Services
Matt Wise	Cardiff and Vale UHB	Research & Development Director

Appendix C. Resources

This is a selection of relevant information resources. The most practically useful toolkits and guides are **highlighted in bold**.

Repository information resources

Resource	URL	Description
Confederation of Open Access Repositories (COAR)	https://coar-repositories.org/	An international association bringing together individual repositories and repository networks to build capacity, align policies and provides guidance on good practice.
COncnecting REpositories (CORE)	https://core.ac.uk/how-core-supports-open-access	A not-for-profit community-governed service which indexes all open access research outputs from repositories and journals worldwide. Provides tools for content discovery, managing content and creating Open Archives Initiative identifiers.
OpenDOAR	https://opendoar.ac.uk/	A Jisc service providing a global directory of quality-assured Open Access Repositories.

General publishing information resources

Resource	URL	Description
Association of Learned and Professional Society Publishers (ALPSP) Library Publishing Special Interest Group	https://www.alpssp.org/our-community/special-interest-groups/library-publishing/	A special interest group for library professionals within the ALPSP international trade association for scholarly publishing, aimed at library publishers and service providers interested in collaboration with library publishers.
Association of University Presses	https://aupresses.org/	A global community of publishers whose mission is to ensure academic excellence and cultivate knowledge.
Chartered Institute of Editing and Proofreading	https://www.ciep.uk/knowledge-hub/suggested-minimum-rates.html	Promotes excellence in English language editing and indicates fees that a freelance editorial professionals could charge for their work.
Committee on Publication Ethics (COPE)	https://publicationethics.org/	Committee on Publication Ethics (COPE) promotes integrity and ethical practice in scholarly communication. Includes guidance and tools including e-learning for members.
World Association of Medical Editors (WAME)	https://www.wame.org/	Voluntary association of editors of peer-reviewed medical journals aiming to foster international editorial cooperation and education. Membership is free.

OA publishing information resources

Resource	URL	Description
cOAlition S	https://www.coalition-s.org/addendum-to-the-coalition-s-guidance-on-the-implementation-of-plans/principles-and-implementation/	An international consortium of research funding and performing organisations who are committed to full and immediate Open Access publication.
DIAMAS Best Practices checklist for Diamond OA publishers	https://diamasproject.eu/best-practices-checklist-for-diamond-oa-publishers/	Checklist to help align publishing activities with the Diamond OA Standard (DOAS) and best practices in Diamond OA publishing.
Diamond Discovery Hub	https://ddh.edch.eu/docs/	Aims to provide a comprehensive registry of institutionally-published and scholar-led OA journals without author fees in Europe, enhancing visibility of diamond OA journals.
Directory of Open Access Books (DOAB)	https://www.doabooks.org/en/publishers/join-doab	Aims to increase the discoverability of OA books. Academic publishers can provide metadata of OA books.
Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ)	https://doaj.org	A unique and extensive index of diverse open access journals from around the world.
European Diamond Capacity Hub	https://edch.eu/	A European collective providing services for Diamond OA publishers, service providers and tools & technology providers.
Jisc New University Press Toolkit	https://www.jisc.ac.uk/guides/new-university-press-toolkit	Toolkit providing guidance for new university presses and library-led publishing ventures. Covers planning, business models, systems, dissemination, marketing and evaluation.
Library Publishing Curriculum	https://librarypublishing.org/resources/library-publishing-curriculum/	Professional development offerings for librarians to empower them to meet local needs to launch and/or enhance scholarly publishing activities.
Open Access Journals Toolkit	https://www.oajournals-toolkit.org/	The Open Access Journals Toolkit covers topics across the journal development lifecycle and everyday operation.
Open Access Publishing in European Networks (OAPEN)	https://oapen.org/ and https://oabooks-toolkit.org/	Independent, not-for-profit Dutch foundation registered at the National Library in The Hague. Dedicated to supporting OA peer-reviewed scholarly books. Toolkit resource supports better understanding of OA publishing.
Open Book Collective	https://openbookcollective.org/	A charity bringing together publishers, publishing service providers, and scholarly libraries to secure the diversity and financial futures of open access book production and dissemination.

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Resource	URL	Description
Open Institutional Publishing Association (OIPA)	https://oipauk.org/	Intended to connect and encourage OA publishing in the UK offering a source of support and advocacy for established and emerging university presses and institutionally-affiliated OA publishing operations.
Open Scholarly Publishing Association (OASPA)	https://www.oaspa.org/	A community of organisations engaged in open scholarship aiming to encourage and enable open access as the predominant model of communication for scholarly outputs. Includes resources, tools and best practice guides.

The Ingenuity Centre, University of Nottingham Innovation Park, Nottingham, NG7 2TU, UK

www.research-consulting.com

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